

Critical Analysis of Laws- Regulating Criminal Investigation in Pakistan

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Abstract

A crime is a fatal factor of the society. It can only be controlled when criminals are countered, and it is possible when they are properly investigated and brought to justice. For the purpose, every state has its own regulatory framework. Pakistan, being a sovereign state, has her own regulatory framework of investigation laws- consisting of procedural laws like Code of the Criminal Procedure 1898, rules like Police Rules 1934 and some directive orders/principles like Police Order 2002 and FIA Act etc. This article will explain all the steps of criminal investigation in Pakistan including common law and laws mentioned above. This article will also highlight some controversial points of legal system in Pakistan like cross FIR etc.

Key words: Investigation, Civilization, Sumerians, Mesopotamia, Abeel, Anti-Rape Act, Cognizable, Daily Diary, Zimni, Challan,

Key Abbreviations: CrPC, PPC, FIA, SP, SHO, IO, SIO, SSOIU, CTD, U/S, LEA, DC, AC, PBUH, PS, etc

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